

Research Article

Folkloric Uses of Birds Species in Akoko North-East Local Government Area of Ondo State

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Abstract

The study assessed the traditional uses of birds and their impact on farming activities in Akoko North East Local Government Area of Ondo State. The data were collected by the use of a structured questionnaire administered to respondents in seven (7) selected out of thirteen (13) ward in the study area questionnaires were administered to twenty (20) respondents from each ward to make total of a hundred and forty (140) questionnaires. The result shows that 23 bird species were sighted during the periods of observation which lasted between December 2016 and June 2017. In the study area, bird species serve different functions which include time indicator (fire bellied woodpecker), source of protein (Kingfisher, Ostrich, Bush fowl), and they were also used to generate income (bush fowl and peacock). Birds also indicate events and seasons e.g. when vultures fly in the mass, it indicates that an important dignitary will die. They also feature in traditional festival such as masquerades and Gudugbe. Some bird species destroy farm products, these include Bush fowl, Village Weaver and Red Eyed Turtle Dove. Stages of attack on plant species cut across all stages from sowing stage to storage stage. In order to reduce the level of destruction, it is hereby recommended that should adopt the scarecrow method in controlling bird species that destroy farm products.

Keywords: Folkloric, Species, Bird, Akoko North East Local Government Area, Questionnaire

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Introduction

The first step into the fascinating world of avian ecology for most people is learning how to identify their local birds (Hill and Peter, 1988). Normally the effort to satisfy this desire, to know which birds that bring fortune, or taboo, and that are visiting their backyard, or that have economic importance to them are the beginning of a lifelong love affair with bird watching so, birds watching is fun, informative and a great way to meet people and learn about the world we live in. Learning how to identify your local birds will require you read up bird behaviors. Though, birds watching is different from birds spotting, because bird watcher is interested in the beauty of the birds and its behavior, while a bird spotter is only interested in collecting a set of stick on a piece of paper (Paul *et al.*, 1988).

Most birds can be identified by a combination of their image and knowledge of the habitat they are in at a point in time. In most parts of the world, there is now a good color guide to the local bird fauna identification.

Identifying birds and their impact on human activities is just like getting to know your human neighbors. Their habit, their shape, their styles of walking and habits, become familiar enough that you can recognize each neighbor immediately, even at a distance. Paying attention to individual differences can help you to identify birds. You can recognize many birds simply by noting their shapes and other useful characteristics like bird posture, size, flight pattern and or flight profile and kind of habitat in which the birds were identified general groups of birds i.e. warblers, flycatchers; hawks, owls, wrens - whose members are all sharing certain similarities. Birds in the same general groups often have the same body shape and proportion, although they may vary in size (Charles, 1990). Silhouette gives many clues to a bird's identity, allowing birders to assign a bird to the correct group or even the exalts species (Gill, 2006).

Birds also have a very strong heart and an efficient way of breathing, which are necessary for birds to fly. They also use a lot of energy while flying and need to eat a lot of food to power their flight. Not all flying animals are birds and not all birds can fly. The ability to fly has developed independently many times throughout the history of the earth (Zhou, 2004). The assessment of some of these wild birds found in this area will help us to document the impact and human belief attached to the existence of these birds and to what existence these birds impact on human activities

Materials and Methods

The study area for this work is Akoko North-East Local Government Area in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State. This local government has vegetation that supports the immigration of bird species that is due to the abundant growth of arable and tree crops. There are tall trees that provide shade where these birds rest and build their nest upon. Due to the presence of different tree species that provide nectar in the area, birds are being attracted and in the process of finding their food, they also help with pollinating tree crops.

Sampling Procedure and Sampling Size

Multi-stage sampling was employed for the purpose of this research. Seven out of the thirteen wards within the Local Government were chosen based on their rural setup and level of involvement in farming activities. A total number of one hundred and forty (140) questionnaires were administered in all the wards i.e. twenty (20) questionnaires in each ward.

Data Collection

On-site assessment of bird species within the study area was carried out to identify bird species present within the study area. The birds were identified with the help of field guides.

The questionnaires that were used to collect data on:

- I. Personal biodata
- II. The belief of people on a different bird species
- III. The level of damage done by these birds on farming activities in the area.

Data Analysis

Frequency, bar chart, and tables were used to present the result on bird and to document a human belief in relation to species present within the study area and to evaluate the impact of birds on farming activities.

Results and Discussions

Bio-personal Data of the Respondents

Table 1-3 shows the frequency structure of the respondents. Forty-three percent (43.30%) of the respondents are within 51-60 years of age, which is the highest while the

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least is 5.80% i.e. 61 and above. 62.50% of the respondents have access to only secondary education this shows that most of the respondents have access to only secondary education this shows that most of the respondents are literate.

Table 1: Frequency Table on the Respondents Age

Age	Frequency (F)	Percentage %
20-30	24	20.0
31-40	10	8.30
41-50	27	22.50
51-60	52	43.30
61 Above	7	5.80
Total	120	100

Table 2: Respondents Primary Occupation

Occupation	Frequency (F)	Percentage %
Farmer	45	37.50
Hunter	8	6.70
Trader	29	24.20
Others	38	31.60
Total	120	100

Table 3: Respondents Educational Background

Occupation	Frequency (F)	Percentage %
Primary	42	35.00
Secondary	75	62.50
No Formal Education	3	2.50
Total	120	100

General Information on Birds Population

Table 4, shows the list of common bird species sighted within the study area. A total of (7) species was sighted in the dry season while (5) species were sighted in the wet season and (13) species were sighted at both seasons. Acciptriadae had the highest number individuals (3 species) while others have either one or two frequencies of the

bird species sighted in each month shows that December has the highest number (69) in the dry season while February has the lowest number (16) in both dry and wet season.

Table 4: Name of the Wild Birds Commonly Seen In the Area

S/NO	LOCAL NAME	COMMON NAME
1.	Awodi	Marital eagle
2.	Elulu	Senegal coucal
3.	Aparo	Bush fowl
4.	Asa	Hawk
5.	Akalamagbo	
6.	Atioro	Black-headed heron
7.	Owiwi	Barn Owl
8.	Adaba	Red-eyed turtle dove
9.	Awo	Guinea fowl
10.	Ogongo	Ostrich
11.	Igun	Vulture
12.	Ega	Village weaver bird
13.	Lekeleke	Cattle Egrets
14.	Okin	Peacock
15.	Eyele	Pigeon
16.	Ayekoto	Parrot
17.	Alapandede	Mosque swallow
18.	Tintin	Bronze maninkin
19.	Aluko	Beaded barbet
20.	Odidere	Long-tailed dove
21.	Eye oba	Swallow
22.	Odere koko	Chestnut mantle
23.	Igbegbe	Black-throated coucal
24.	Akoko lugi	Fire-bellied woodpecker
25.	Eye omi	Kingfisher

The bird species sighted feeds on various food items including insects, seeds, grains, and flesh. Table 6, however, shows that eleven (11) of the bird species feed on insects these include Swallow, Black-throated coucal, fire-bellied woodpecker, Culture, king fisher e.t.c. are flesh eaters while pigeon, red-eyed turtle dove, bush fowl, feed on grains such as maize and guinea corn. Other species such as bronze maninkin, village weaverbird e.t.c. feed only on the small seed of crops.

The various benefits derived from bird species in the study area are listed in table 7. The respondents agreed that one of the bird species serve as a time indicator. This is fire bellied woodpecker, most of the bird species serve as a source of protein, which supplements protein intake in most families.

Table 5: Names of Birds Classified Based On Their Species and Families

S/NO	LOCAL NAME	COMMON NAME	SPECIES	FAMILY
1.	Awodi	Black kite	<i>Milvous migrans</i>	Accipitridae
2.	Elulu	Senegal coucal	<i>Centropus senegalesis</i>	Trochilidae
3.	Aparo	Bush fowl	<i>Francolinus</i>	Phasianidae
4.	Asa konko	Grasshopper buzzard	<i>Bustaztur rufipennis</i>	Accipitridae
5.	Akalamagbo			
6.	Atioro	Black-headed heron	<i>Ardea melanocephala</i>	Ardeidae
7.	Owiwi	Barn Owl	<i>Tyto alba</i>	Tytonidae
8.	Adaba	Red-eyed turtle dove	<i>Streptopetia semitorquata</i>	Akidae
9.	Awo	Guinea fowl	<i>Numida meleageis</i>	Accipitridae
10.	Ogongo	Ostrich	<i>Phoenicopteridae</i>	Phoenicopteridae
11.	Igun	Vulture	<i>Aegyptius monachus</i>	Accipitridae
12.	Ega	Village weaver bird	<i>Ploceus cucullatus</i>	Ploccidac
13.	Lekeleke	Cattle eagrets	<i>Ardola ibis</i>	Ardeidae
14.	Okin	Pea cock	<i>Balearica Padonila</i>	Rallidae
15.	Eyele	Pigeon	<i>Columba palumbus</i>	Alcidae
16.	Ayekoto	Parrot	<i>Poicepha robustus</i>	Charadriidae
17.	Alapandede	Mosque swallow	<i>Hirundo senegalenses</i>	Fringillidae
18.	Tintin	Bronze maninkin	<i>Lonchura cucullatus</i>	Ploceidae
19.	Aluko	Beaded barbet	<i>Lybius dubius</i>	Motacillidae
20.	Odidere	Long-tailed dove	<i>Oena capensis</i>	charadriidae
21.	Eye oba	Swallow	<i>Hirundo leucosoma</i>	fringillidae
22.	Odere koko	Chestnut mantle	<i>Bathmocerrcus rufus</i>	sylviidae
23.	Igbegbe	Black-throated coucal	<i>Centropus leucogestes</i>	Cuculidae
24.	Akoko lugi	Fire-bellied woodpecker	<i>Mesopicos gocetae</i>	Picidae
25.	Eye omi	Kingfisher	<i>Haleyon Spp</i>	Alcedinidae

Table 6: Benefit Derived From Birds by the Respondents

Birds	Time indicator	Source of protein	Medicine	Income	Other
Marital eagle		+		+	
Senegal coucal				+	+
Bush fowl		+		+	
Hawk		+			+
Akalamagbo				+	+
Black-headed heron				+	+
Barn Owl		+	+		
Red-eyed turtle dove		+		+	
Guinea fowl		+		+	
Ostrich		+		+	+
Vulture			+	+	
Village weaver bird				+	+
Cattle Egrets				+	+
Peacock				+	+
Pigeon		+		+	+
Parrot				+	+
Mosque swallow				+	+
Bronze maninkin				+	+
Aluko		+		+	+
Long-tailed dove			+		
Swallow					+
Chestnut mantle					+
Black-throated coucal					+
Fire-bellied woodpecker	+				+
Kingfisher		+			

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Cultural Belief

From time immemorial people never associated birds with various events which made them believe that some birds are significantly and highly sacred. Table 8 shows the list of some birds and human belief associated with such birds.

Table 7: List of Birds That Is Forbidden For the People

Birds	Condition	Believes
Vulture	Flying in mass	It is a Bad sign, that an important person will die
Vulture	When killed	Whoever kills it will die within a year
Akalamagbo	When killed	Whoever kills it will die within a month
Swallow	Resided	Whenever it resides in a house, it signifies peace.
Bam Owl	When it makes an incomplete call/sound.	When it makes an incomplete sound at night, it signifies bad omen.
Cattle egret	It is forbidden to be eaten	When killed within five (5) minutes its meat turn black

All these birds listed above had been regarded as sacred for the people. This belief is still respected. Also, the birds listed above are also accepted by the people, that whoever kills them has violated or committed a crime regarded as taboos and the person will not go unpunished except in cases where prescribed rituals are required to shift the curse on the offenders.

Festivals and the Use of birds

Table 8 shows the list of festivals celebrated in the community.

Table 8: List of Birds and Parts Used In Festival in the Study Area

Festivals	Birds used	Birds part used	Month of celebration
New yam	-	-	June
Masquerade	Aluko	Feathers	April-May
Arigiga	-	-	April-May
Popoloro	-	-	Once in a year as prescribed
Gudugbe	Odidere	Feathers	February
Imale	Pigeon	Feathers and Heads	April-May

The feather of Aluko bird used during the Masquerade festival is to add color to their outing, the same thing is applicable to Gudugbe while that of the Imale, the feather, and the head is for rituals during the celebration. The information gathered also from the respondents' shows that some birds are used during the coronation of Oba/Chiefs. The birds are listed in Table 9 and the parts used. The part used are for rituals during the coronation of the Oba/Chiefs Though, before using they are usually preserved if when not used in the fresh form, they are preserved in palm kernel oil (adin) to protect them against drying and is regarded as the best way of traditional preservation of bird feather.

Medicinal Importance of Birds

It is gathered that few of the birds are used or medicinal purpose; they are listed in Table 9.

Table 9: Birds Used For Medicinal Ailment

BIRDS	PART USED	AILMENT
Pigeon	Whole heart	Fever/malaria
Vulture	Feather	To apply medicine for treating measles
Long-tailed dove	Whole heart	Prevention against premature death

Table 10: Seasonal Significance of Birds

BIRDS	SEASONS	SIGNIFICANCE
Mosque swallow	Wet season	The beginning of the rainy season
Cattle Egrets	Dry season	The beginning of the dry season
Village weaver bird	Wet season	Fruiting season
Bronze manikin	Wet season	Fruiting season

Impact of Birds on Farming Activities in the Area

The emergence of some of these wild birds has a great or severe effects on the farming activities in the area as they seriously attacked the planting crops most especially during the planting season. Some of these birds and the crop plant they attacked were listed in Table 11.

Table 11: List of Crops Attacked By Bird Species

Birds	<i>Crops</i>						
	Ma	Pe	Gu	Ca	Rice	Co	Okro
Bush fowl	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Village weaver bird	+		+		+		
Bronze manikin	+		+		+		
Pigeon	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Red eyed turtle dove	+	+	+	+	+		+

Ma - Maize, Pe - Pepper, Gu - Guinea corn, Ca - Cassava, Co - cocoyam

Table 11 shows that birds like Bush fowl, pigeon, and red-eyed turtle dove are the birds that attacked these crops most and follow by a village weaver bird and bronze manikin that has the least effect on the destruction or attacked the crops. This is in line with (Inal and Akinola, 2005), which describes village Weaver and Red Eyed Turtle Dove as a major pest of grain. The stages and level of bird's destruction and attacked is also represented in Table 12:-

Let the following letters represent the different stages

- Sowing stage - +
- Germination stage - O
- Fruiting stage - *
- Flowering stage - □
- Storage - Q

• Ma - Maize, Pe - Pepper, Gu - Guinea corn, Ca - cassava, Co -Cocoyam, Ok - Okro and Ri - Rice*

Table 12: Stage of Attack on Plant Species

Birds	<i>Crops</i>						
	Ma	Pe	Gu	Ca	Ri	Co	Ok
Bush fowl	+OQ	+Q	+QO	Q	+Q	Q	+O
Village weaver bird	* □		* □		* □		
Bronze Manikin	* □		* □		* □		
Pigeon	Q	Q	Q	Q	Q	Q	Q
Red eyed turtle dove	Q+O	Q+O	Q+O	Q	Q	Q	Q+

Table 12 shows these birds almost destroyed the plant crops at almost all stages starting from the sowing stage to dry and storage stage.

Table 13 shows the degree of level of damage done by the birds. The level of damage will be represented by letters as:

Mild damage - M
 Average damage - A
 Severe damage - S

Table 13: Level of Damage Caused By Birds Species

Damage	<i>Crops</i>						
	Ma	Pe	Gu	Ca	Ri	Co	Ok
Average damage		+					+
Severe damage	+		+		+		
Mild damage				+		+	

Table 13 shows that maize, okro and guinea corn were severely damaged or attacked by these birds; in controlling these damaged some measures were adopted by the farmers like hunting, trapping and scarecrow. In which scarecrow happened to be the most adopted in controlling these destructions. Scarecrow is the process by which the farmers erect a tree and on top of the tree erected is a black or white nylon and sometimes they place rag clothes on the erected tree which will scare away the birds and thereby reduce their level of attacks. Though, some farmers are involved in hunting these birds either for souvenirs, sell and mostly for eating.

Apart from those birds that are commonly seen in all season, the appearance of some birds in a particular season could signify a special event, like early wet seasons, and some signify dry season e.g. Mistle thrush for the wet season and swan for the dry season.

Table 13 and Fig. 1 show that most of these birds are commonly seen at evening time when they are going back to their nest for resting and at this time of the day, is the period when most of them search for food and their prey and the weather condition also favour their outing while during the morning time, they are not normally looked at or watched by the people, and during the afternoon they go to hide due to hot weather, except few that will be swearing around for leisure or due to some reason or condition that warrant them or force them out. The result is in accordance with (Inal *et al.*, 1999) that suggested 6.00am-8.00am and 4.00pm-6.00pm as the best period when birds can be easily sighted. Watching birds in the wild have been on the interested game, but due to the extinction of most of these birds have made people to be discouraged from watching them.

The following wild bird species have gone to extinction or are no more seen in the environment. They are Ostrich, Barn Owl, Woodpecker, Locust bird, and Village weaver bird e.t.c. due to human activities find a means of controlling their impact on human activities and the following are some of the human activities like hunting, deforestation, bush burning and continuous farm clearing which has destroyed their habitat.

Discussion

The study was carried out on the uses of birds, their impact on human activities and the beliefs attached to it by man. Bio-personal data of the respondents indicate 43.3% are within 51-60 years of age, while only 5.80% are within 61 above years. However, most of the people that engage in farming activities are adult's people indicating that the oncoming generations do not rely on farming as their primary source of income. The majority of these respondents depend primarily on farming as their source of income while very few have alternatives.

About 62.50% of the respondents are literate up to secondary school and 35.00% are primary school education respectively. This shows that farmers around the study area are not versed in education and this affects their level of interest in watching birds in the wild.

Seasonal Variations in Bird Species Sighted

The climatic difference has brought about seasonal variation of bird sightedness. As most of the bird species sighted during the dry season are the birds that are mostly flesh eaters and they also find it easy to sight their prey where the bush has dried or clear of 36.70% of these birds are seasonal bird species found in this area as cattle egret, vulture e.t.c. and 19.2% are commonly sighted during the wet season like a mosque swallow, black weaver e.t.c. due to the availability of the types of their feeds and is the period of early fruiting while, the bird species sighted at all season is 44.20% because their feeds, e.g. insects are seen all the time and they are very common in the environment, bird species like Senegal coucah e.t.c.

Feeding Habit of Bird Species

Eleven (11) of the bird species in the area is insect eaters which includes cattle egret, fire-bellied woodpecker, and Senegal coucah This acuity on feeding insects has a great impact on farming activities. These impacts are both positive and negative in that some of the insects caters such as long tail night jar feed on an insect that could destroy planted crop while some like the double spurred Francolin feed on crops valued by farmers.

Some birds like a black kite, grasshopper buzzard, lizard buzzard, and grey heron, however, feed on the flesh of animals such as rats, lizards, and chicks. The particular species were not seen during the wet season. This could be attributed to the dense

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vegetation during this period, which could impair visibility of birds. Thus, their sight could not penetrate to the floor of the forest for food. This forced them to move to the area where they can get food only to come back in the dry season.

However, some birds including a black weaver and village weaver feed on cultivated grains which are highly treasured by farmers. They are regarded as a nuisance by farmers who control them using scarecrows and same times trapping. This forced them to move to the area where they can get food only to come back in the dry season.

However, some birds including a black weaver and village weaver feed on cultivated grains which are highly treasured by farmers. They are regarded as a nuisance by farmers who control them using scarecrow and sometimes trapping.

Beliefs and Benefits Derived By Respondents

Birds are not much valued by people in the study area due to the low interest they developed in them. But some still show a kind of interest because of their uses as they use some bird species as a medicine like vulture feathers use as a self defense during the masquerade festival and its feather is used as the color for masquerade outing decoration and Odidere feather is used to treat pre-matured death. Bird species like fire bellied woodpecker is used as a time indicator, they do indicate the time at every hour during the day.

Most of the bird species found in the study area are a source of protein for the respondents. However, other such as cattle egret, black manikin e.t.c. are not eaten due to various belief of the people. For example, the vulture is not eaten because it is generally believed to be a mysterious bird while, black manikin is not eaten because of its small size while the cattle egret is not eaten because its skin becomes dark when killed.

Although some of the birds serve as a direct source of income to the respondents, they are still highly valued because of their supplementary values. These include the use of their feather in the preparation of local tie and dye fabrics. The feather of some of the birds such as black kite and cattle egret is used in adding pattern to the fabrics. Some of the bird species are major ingredients in the preparation of some traditional medicine portion.

Conclusion

The site assessment of the bird species within the study area was carried out with the help of a field guide and sets of questionnaires administered to the respondents. The result revealed that bird species have an impact on the life of the people living in the locality. As some bird species are used to cure some illness and diseases, e.g. pigeon, Vulture, e.t.c. Some are for time watch e.g. Fire-bellied woodpecker, Some are to indicate particular season, Cattle egrets and most of them are a source of income and protein-like Bush fowl, Peacock, Pigeon e.t.c. And some of this bird species have also helped to pollinate the farmers planting crops, bronze manikin and as some also help involve in destroying their products village weaver bird. But, most of this bird's species are not commonly seen in the area due to the activities of the people living hill the area.

Recommendation

The government should organize a regular seminar where people of the area will be enlightened on the importance of birds and reason why they should be protected. Extension agencies should educate the farmers on how to protect their harassed crops. There should be more regular enlightenment on the reason why all the wild bird species that are going to extinct or not commonly sighted should be preserved for generations to come.

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